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Research Article

FREQUENCY OF IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA AND B THALASSEMIA TRAIT IN FEMALE MEDICAL STUDENTS AT UMM AL-QURA UNIVERSITY IN THE MAKKAH REGION

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Abstract:

Background: iron deficiency anemia (IDA) and beta thalassemia trait (βTT) are the main causes of microcytic hypochromic anemia. Objectives: was to detect the frequency of IDA & βTT among female medical student at Umm Al Qura university (UQU) and to determine the factors associated with IDA in this population. Methods: This study included 214 female students. They were from different medical colleges at UQU. All were subjected to A multiple questionnaires to determine if there was a risk factor for IDA or a positive family history of βTT or major. Measurement of serum iron, serum ferritin, total iron binding capacity, hemoglobin A2 and complete blood count. Results. 177 (82.7%) were normal and 37 (17.29%) were anemic. Out of the 37 anemics, 33(15.42%) were IDA, 2(0.93%) were βTT and 2 (0.93%) were combined IDA and βTT. In the group of iron deficiency anemia, 45.7% taking non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, 20% had heavy menses, 11.4% had gastritis, 2.9% had parasitic infestation, 0% had restriction of diet and 0% had piles. There was a significant association with gastritis when compared to the non anemic group <0.05. There was significant decrease in red cell counts, serum iron and HbA2 levels in those with IDA and βTT than βTT cases. Conclusion: 17.3% of our students are anemic. 15.42% are IDA and 1.9 are βTT (0.93% are βTT and 0.93% are combined IDA and βTT). IDA is one of the co-existing conditions in βTT. Further studies are needed to clarify this point.

Keywords: anemia, IDA, βTT

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INTRODUCTION:

Anemia is a global health problem in developed and developing countries. According to the world health organization the prevalence of anemia in the world is 24.4% that means it affected 1.62 billion of the population. It occurs in all age groups, and is more prevalent among pregnant women and young children (WHO.,2011; Peyrin-Biroulet *et al.*,2015)

Anemia has been shown to affect mental development and learning capacity (Alquaiz *et al.*, 2015) According to the WHO, the most common type of anemia is iron deficiency anemia that affecting 30% of population in the third world. In Saudi Arabia, the prevalence of iron deficiency anemia is 30–56% and the frequent causes of it in female are losing of iron in heavy menstruation, pregnancy and poor diet (World Bank group 2018; Al Hassan.,2015; Al-Sayes *et al.*, 2011). Many studies were done on the prevalence of iron deficiency anemia in different parts of Saudi Arabia in female students and in other population (Al Hassan,2015; Al-Sayes *et al.*, 2011; Al Quaiz *et al.*., 2013; Gari , 2008; Al-Assaf, 2007; Hesham *et al.*,2017).

β - thalassemia is the widest spread genetic disease, about 60,000 a year are diagnosed as β -thalassemia patients (De Sanctis *et al.*,2017). The thalassemsias are a group of disorders in which the normal ratio of alpha and beta globin chain is disrupted. In β -thalassemia, there is decrease production or absence of the β -chain and excess of the alpha chain. The excess chain precipitate and causes destruction of red blood cell precursors in the bone marrow (ineffective erythropoiesis) and circulation (hemolysis). As a result, affected individuals have variable degrees of anemia and extramedullary hematopoiesis, which in turn can cause bone changes, impaired growth, and iron overload (Al-Awamy, 2000).

The Beta -thalassemia is predominant in Asia, the Mediterranean basin, and the Middle East. The WHO estimated that at least 7% of the world's populations are genetic carriers for abnormal hemoglobin (WHO,2008) . Many studies were done on different regions in Saudi Arabia for determination of the prevalence of beta thalassemia trait (Memish and Saeedi,2011; Al-Suliman,2006).

Aim of study

The aim of this study was to detect the frequency of IDA & β TT among females medical student at UQU and to determine the factors associated with IDA among females medical student at Umm Al-Qura University (UQU).

Subjects and methods

A cross-sectional observational study was done through year 2016–2018.

Subjects

The analytical methods of this study were carried out in the laboratory of king Abdul-Aziz hospital and laboratory of hematology and immunology department, faculty of medicine, Umm alQura University in accordance with the approved guidelines. The Umm AlQura University ethics committee approved the protocol of this study. All participants gave informed consent according to the declaration of Helsinki. This study was carried out from January 2016 to January 2018; it included 214 female students aged between 17-26 year. They were from different medical colleges of Umm AlQura University. They were divided into anemic and non anemic according to the levels of hemoglobin. The cut off was ≥ 12 g/dl in the non-anemic group and < 12 in the anemic group (non -pregnant) < 11 in pregnant (World Bank group 2018). The severity of anemia was classified into three stages: mild (>10 g/dL), moderate (7–10 g/dL), or severe (Hb < 7 g/dL) (Al Hassan.,2015).

Sample collection

4 ml of blood sample was collected from each participant under complete aseptic conditions. 2 ml of blood was dispensed into a tube containing EDTA as anticoagulant substances for performing complete blood count, and the measurement of hemoglobin A2 by column chromatography. The complete blood count was done on the same day of collection. The remaining of the sample was kept at 4°C for hemoglobin A2 determination which was done within one week of collection. The other 2ml was collected in plain tubes, left to clot, then separation of serum was done. It was used for determination of serum iron, serum ferritin and TIBC.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

All female students were included. Students with microcytic hypochromic anemia with normal iron profile and normal hemoglobin electrophoresis were excluded from the study as they may be alpha thalassemia trait.

METHOD:

All students were subjected to the following:

1- A multiple questionnaires were applied to the students to determine if there was a risk factor for iron deficiency anemia or a positive family history of beta thalassemia major or trait or a positive case of

beta thalassemia trait. For the iron deficiency anemia, the questions were included, if they followed particular dietary regimens, if the menses was heavy or not, which was identified by the number of packs/day and the duration of the menses. Also, history of piles or peptic ulcer, history of taking non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, history of taking antacids, and history of parasitic infestation. In addition, if there was a past history of taking iron tablets. Moreover, the questions of beta thalassemia include, if there was a family history of thalassemia major or minor and the ethnic origin of the family.

2- Complete hemogram analysis on sysmex XT2000iv which include the following parameters: White blood cell count total and differential, platelets count and RBC's count. The hemoglobin concentration, the packed cell volume, the mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), the mean cell volume (MCV), the mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) and the red cell distribution width (RDW).

3- Estimation of Hb A2 by column chromatography (Helena laboratories, beaumont, TX)

4- Determination of serum iron and TIBC on dimension max siemens.

5- Measurement of serum ferritin on cobas e 411 Roche Hitachi.

Statistical analysis:

The statistical analysis of this study was done using SPSS program version 20. Quantitative data were described in the form of mean \pm SD for the normally distributed data. For the data that was not normally distributed, the median, minimum and maximum were used. The comparisons between groups were performed by using student t test, the Mann Whitney U test and the Anova test. The chi square test and the fisher exact test were used for comparison of qualitative data. A $P \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

The results of this study are summarized in the table from 1-4. This study was applied on 214 female medical students. Their age ranged between 17-26 years with a mean average of 19.6 years. The non-anaemic group was 177 (82.71%), the anaemic group was 37 (17.29%). Out of the 37, 33 (15.4%) were iron deficiency anemia, 2 (0.93%) were beta thalassemia trait (β TT) and 2 (0.93%) were combined IDA and β TT. Table 1 and figure 1. Out of the 37, 30 were had mild anemia and 7 were had moderate anemia.

Table 1: Frequency of IDA & BTT among female medical students at UQU.

	All	Non-Anemic	Anemic	Anemic		
				IDA	β TT	IDA+ β TT
Number	214	177	37	33	2	2
Percentage	%	82.71	17.29	15.42	0.93	0.93

The comparison between both groups (anemic and non-anemic) are shown in Table 2:

There were no significant differences between the two groups with regards to age and white blood cells count $P > 0.05$. There was significant decrease in hemoglobin level, hematocrit, mean cell volume, mean corpuscular hemoglobin, serum iron and serum ferritin between anemic and non-anemic group $p \leq 0.05$. In addition, there were significant increase in the platelets count, red blood cell count, red cell distribution width, hemoglobin A2 and total iron binding capacity between the anemic and non anemic group respectively $P \leq 0.05$.

Table 2: Comparison between anemic & non-anemic group with regards to the clinical and laboratory data.

	Anemic group (n=37) Mean \pm SD	Non-anemic (n=177) Mean \pm SD	P value And Significance
Age/year	19.2 \pm 1.0	19.66 \pm 1.3	0.052
Median	19	19	NS
Min- Max*	17-21	18-26	
WBC X10 ⁹ /l	6.9 \pm 1.86	7.3 \pm 1.95	0.256
Median	6.6	7.2	NS
Min- Max	3.35-11.07	3.36-13.6	
RBC X10 ¹²	4.8 \pm 0.51	4.5 \pm 0.3	0.007
Median	4.8	4.5	S
Min- Max	3.5-6.2	3.83-5.45	
Hb g/dl	10.7 \pm 1.0	13 \pm 0.7	0.000
Median	11.1	13.1	HS
Min – Max	8.2-11.9	11.5-14.8	
HCT%	33.9 \pm 2.7	39.2 \pm 2.2	0.000
Median	34.1	39	HS
Min – Max	27.1-38.2	34.9-45.7	
MCV /fl	72.05 \pm 7.0	87.2 \pm 4.7	0.000
Median	73.4	87	HS
Min – Max	52.4-80.0	79-99.1	
MCH /pg	23.0 \pm 2.5	29.2 \pm 1.6	0.000
Median	23.8	29.4	HS
Min – Max	16.4-25.9	26-33.3	
Platelets X10 ⁹ /l	309.0 \pm 65.6	271.3 \pm 55.8	0.001
Median	304	267	S
Min – Max	165-479	151-486	
RDW SD	17.1 \pm 2.3	13.5 \pm 0.9	0.000
Median	16.6	13.4	HS
Min – Max	12.0-22.4	11.2-15.7	
Ferritin ug/dl	8.3 \pm 7.03	50.9 \pm 24.9	0.000
Median	7.1	46	HS
Min – Max	1.34-42.6	14.0-99.0	
Serum iron ug/dl	19.7 \pm 16.6	65.3 \pm 12.7	0.000
Median	13	67	HS
Min-Max	12-67	45-123	
TIBC	459.0 \pm 47.0	280.0 \pm 21.9	0.000
Median	466	280.0	HS
Min-Max	255-490	250-370	
Hemoglobin A2	2.9 \pm 1.1	2.5 \pm 0.26	0.031
Median	2.6	2.4	S
Min-Max	2.0-7.0	1.9-3.0	

Min* = Minimum, Max*= Maximum, NS* = non-significant, HS* = high significant, S* = Significant. WBC= white blood cells. RBC = red blood cells. Hb = hemoglobin. MCV = meancorpuscular hemoglobin. MCH= mean corpuscular hemoglobin. RDW= red cell distribution width. TIBC= total iron binding capacity.

The comparison between different anemic groups studied are shown in table 3

Significant increase of red blood cells, white blood cells, serum iron and hemoglobin A2 was found in the beta thalassemia trait p<0.05. No other significant differences were detected. Table3.

Table 3: comparison between different studied anemic groups.

	IDA (n=33) Mean ± SD	Beta TT(n=2) Mean ± SD	Combined IDA & βTT (n=2) Mean ± SD	P and significance
Age/year	19.1 ± 1.0	20	20	.152 NS
Median	19	20	20	
Min- Max*	17-21	20-20	20-20	
WBC X10 ⁹ /l	6.9 ± 1.86	8.8 ± 0.22	4.49 ± 63.0	0.035 S
Median	6.6	8.8	4.49	
Min- Max	3.53-11.07	8.7-9.0	4.05-4.49	
RBC X10 ¹²	4.6 ± 0.4	6.0 ± 0.28	5.25 ± 0.28	0.009 S
Median	4.7	6.0	5.25	
Min- Max	3.5-5.2	5.8-6.2	5.05-5.44	
Hb g/dl	10.7 ± 1.0	11.75 ± 0.07	9.9 ± 0.41	0.080 NS
Median	11.1	11.75	9.9	
Min – Max	8.2-11.9	11.7-11.8	8.9-10.9	
HCT%	34.0 ± 2.6	34.5 ± 0.7	31.2 ± 3.81	0.386 NS
Median	34.3	34.5	31.2	
Min – Max	27.1-38.2	34.0-35.0	28.5-33.9	
MCV /fl	73.3 ± 5.6	63.9 ± 12.58	59.7 ± 10.3	0.062 NS
Median	74.9	63.9	59.7	
Min – Max	57.9-80.0	55-72.8	52.4-67.1	
MCH /pg	23.3 ± 2.1	22.1 ± 4.38	19.0 ± 3.68	0.145 NS
Median	24.0	22.1	19	
Min – Max	17.2-25.9	19-25.2	16.4-21.6	
Platelets X10 ⁹ /l	308.4 ± 68.7	318.0 ± 52.3	315.0 ± 28.3	0.934 NS
Median	304	318	315	
Min – Max	165-479	281.0-355.0	295.0-335.0	
RDW SD	17.3 ± 1.8	12.7 ± 0.98	18.6 ± 5.3	0.062 NS
Median	16.7	12.7	18.6	
Min – Max	14.5-21.0	12.0-13.4	14.9-22.4	
Ferritin ug/dl	7.0 ± 3.7	29.3 ± 18.8	6.3 ± 6.6	0.053 NS
Median	5.9	29.3	6.3	
Min – Max	1.34-12.0	16.0-42.6	1.7-11.0	
Serum iron ug/dl	17.3 ± 7.0	56.0 ± 15.5	23.0 ± 15.6	0.038 S
Median	12	56	23.0	
Min-Max	12-35	45-67	12.0-34.0	
Total iron binding capacity	469.6 ± 11.9	272.5 ± 24.7	469.5 ± 27.6	0.060 NS
Median	467	272.5	469.5	
Min-Max	450-490	255-290	450.0-489.0	
Hemoglobin A2	2.6 ± 0.24	6.75 ± 0.35	4.45 ± 0.35	.005 S
Median	2.5	6.75	4.45	
Min-Max	2.0-3.0	6.5-7.0	4.2-4.7	

The comparison between iron deficiency anemia and non-iron deficiency anemia with regards to the risk factors. Table 4.

In the group of iron deficiency anemia versus non iron deficiency anemia, it was observed that 45.7% taking non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs versus 39.1%, 20% had heavy menses versus 11.2%, 11.4% had gastritis versus 3.3%, 2.9% had parasitic infestation versus 0%, no one had restriction of diet versus 5% and no one had piles

versus 0.6%. Only, there was significant association with gastritis. <0.05. No other significant associations were detected P>0.05.

Table 4: Comparison between iron deficiency anemia and non- iron deficiency anemia (beta thalassemia trait & normal) with regards to predisposing factor.

Risk Factors		Iron deficiency anemia No=35	Non- iron deficiency anemia No= 179	P Value & significant
Diet	yes	0(0%)	9(5.0%)	0.361 NS
	No	35(100%)	170(95.0%)	
Menses	yes	7(20%)	20(11.2%)	0.166 NS
	No	28(80%)	159(88.2%)	
Gastritis	Yes	4(11.4%)	3(3.3%)	0.015 S
	No	31(88.6)	176(96.7%)	
Piles	Yes	0(0%)	1(0.6%)	1.0 NS
	No	35(100%)	178(99.4%)	
NSAID	Yes	16(45.7%)	70(39.1%)	0.572 NS
	No	19(54.3%)	109(60.9)	
Parasitic infestation	Yes	1(2.9%)	0(0%)	0.164NS
	No	34(97.1%)	179(100%)	
No of pads	yes	6(17.1%)	23(12.8%)	0.588 NS
	No	29(82.9%)	156(87.2%)	
Duration of menses	Yes	11(31.4%)	63(35.2%)	0.703 NS
	No	24(68.6%)	116(64.8%)	

φ Menses: yes = heavy flow, no = normal flow. *No of pads = Number of pads yes => 3, no ≤ 3. # duration : yes => 4

days, no ≤ 4.

Family history of beta thalassemia major and trait in female medical students:

3 out of 214(0.93%) had positive family history of beta thalassemia major. 1 out of 214(0.46%) had positive family history of beta thalassemia trait.

History of taking iron therapy:

9(25.7%) of the iron deficiency anemia group were taking iron tablets versus 40(22.3%) of the non iron deficiency anemia group. In the group of iron deficiency anemia 80% not taking iron therapy, 5.7% had a history of recent iron therapy and 14.3% had a past history of taking iron therapy. In the non- iron deficiency group 80.4% were not taking iron therapy, 5.6% had a history of recent iron therapy and 14.0% had a past history of taking iron therapy i.e. 19.6% had a positive past history of taking iron therapy.

DISCUSSION:

Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) and thalassemia syndromes, especially beta thalassemia trait (βTT), are the most common causes of microcytic hypochromic anemias in Saudi Arabia. The study of the prevalence of anemia in female students has been

increased. They are at a high risk of deficiency because of the bad habits of food, and their potentially high nutritional demands due to menstrual blood loss, pregnancy, and/or lactation (Fayet-Moore et al., 2014; Shill et al., 2014; Shams et al., 2010).

The present study focused on establishing the frequency of IDA and βTT among Saudi female medical students at Umm Al-Qura University and identifying the risk factors associated with IDA. The present work identified an overall frequency of anemia as 17.29%. Out of them, 15.42% with pure IDA, 1.86% with βTT (0.93% pure BTT and 0.93% combined IDA and βTT). Our results are decreased in comparison with earlier national results. They reported that, the prevalence of anemia among women of reproductive age (15-49 year) was 42.9 in 2016 and was 55.50 in 1990 (World Bank group 2018). In our study, it was found that 19.6% of the non-anemic group had a positive history of iron therapy. This may denote that the frequency of anemia is higher than the recorded one (36.89%) and it was decreased due to therapy. On the contrary, the overall prevalence of anemia in developed countries

was lower(WHO Global Database). Among female Saudi university students in Saudi Arabia, a previous study observed IDA (64%) while other recent study showed a much lower rate 12.5% which is nearly similar to our result(Al Hassan.,2015; Alzaheb and Al-Amer,2017).

In the current study, IDA might be attributed to various factors as increasing iron demands during puberty, menstrual losses, limited and faulty dietary iron intake, parasitic infestation, intake of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and history of gastritis. The significant risk factor on the frequency of IDA in UQU students was history of gastritis (11.4%, P: 0.015). Moreover, the sedentary lifestyle and the fast-food intake have been associated with IDA (Aderibigbe *et al.*, 2014). In our IDA group, it was found that 14.3% had a history of taking iron therapy. This indicates that the IDA is recurrent as long as the predisposing factors are present and not treated. It is essential to detect the predisposing factors of IDA among female university students and to increase the public health attention towards the IDA and its prevention.

Beta thalassemia major has poor impact on the life of the affected individual if untreated probably. The detection of the carrier state is very important to decrease the occurrence of the disease. Saudi Arabia is well-known for its diverse frequency of β -thalassaemia carriers among different regions(Memish and Saeedi,2011; Alenazi *et al.*,2015; El-Tayeb *et al.*,2008).

In this study the frequency of beta thalassemia trait (β TT) was 1.9% in the female medical students. It is lower than the previous study done by the premarital screening system who studied the prevalence rate of beta thalassemia trait in pre-married couples in different parts of Saudi Arabia from 2011 to 2015. The lowest frequency was found in Najran (2.4%) and the highest was in eastern region (23.7%). The prevalence rate in the Makkah region was 14.4%(Alsaeed *et al.*,2018). Our study is done in small group of female students in comparison to the study done by the premarital screening program.

Studies from other Arab countries showed that the frequency of β TT in general falls within the range of 2.0–10.0%(Belhoul *et al.*,2013).

In our study, the occurrence of IDA in patients with β TT was 0.93%. This is due to the lack of iron in these cases. Previously, it has long been well-thought-out that IDA does not exist in thalassemia

syndromes. Similar to earlier authors who have demonstrated lower hemoglobin levels in patients with coexisting IDA and β TT(Alperin *et al.*,1977; Qureshi *et al.*, 1997; Dolai *et al.*,2012). our patients showed non-significant lower levels (9.9 ± 4.1 vs 11.75 ± 0.07). However, significant changes have been observed in both red blood cell counts (6.0 ± 0.28 Vs 5.25 ± 0.028 , P; 0.009) and serum iron (56.0 ± 15.5 Vs 23.0 ± 15.6 , P: 0.038). Interestingly, HbA2 levels have been shown to be lower in patients with coexisting IDA and β TT (6.75 ± 0.35 Vs 4.45 ± 0.35 , P: 0.005). Fortunately, our cases have hemoglobin A2 levels above the cut off value for the diagnosis of β TT. In other cases, the reduction in HbA2 levels in patients with concomitant β TT and IDA has been suggested to interfere with the diagnosis of the former. Previous studies have hypothesized that such an occurrence can lead to these patients with β TT marrying another person with β TT with a risk of birth of thalassemia major child (Alenazi *et al.*, 2015; Usman *et al.*,2011) Although an extensive search of this issue had been well studied, no Saudi reports of concomitant β TT and iron deficiency, our study is the first to declare this point.

This study was subjected to some limitations; no causal associations could be established between the influencing factors and personal IDA due to the cross-sectional nature of the study and small sample size. The relative frequency in overall female population cannot be judged from these data as this study was done on a specific group of population that may not reflect the true prevalence.

CONCLUSIONS:

This study observed an overall frequency of anemia as 17.3% with IDA (15.4%) and β TT (1.9%) among its sample of apparently healthy young Saudi female university students with gastritis is the main risk factor in relation to contracting IDA. Other important finding suggests that IDA is one of the co-existing conditions in β TT. So, it could provide a new epidemiological data on prevalence of IDA and β TT among University female students in Makkah that can serve as a baseline for future studies and interventions. Further follow up large size studies are necessary to evaluate the long-term impact of screening this age group.

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Author contributions

A.Z.: the idea and the design of the study, did the statistical analysis, share in preparing the tables, the writing and revising of the main manuscript. **NS:** share in statistical analysis, preparing the tables, the writing and revising of the main manuscript. **NB** share in preparing the tables, the writing and revising of the main manuscript. **MA** share in the laboratory work. **AS, DJ, KB, MM, RM, RK, SA** and **WA** collection of the samples and data, the preparation of the master table for statistical analysis and share in the writing of the manuscript.

Disclosure of interest: the authors report no conflict of interest

Ethics approval The Umm AlQura University ethics committee approved the protocol of this study.

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